

INSURANCE AND INCOME STATUS AND MENTAL HEALTH UTILIZATION
AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

by

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Project Abstract

Insurance coverage has proven to be an influential factor in individuals' willingness to seek out mental health services, as well as the type of services they may choose to utilize. In recent years, educational institutions have also encouraged their students to reach outwards toward support systems, especially those enrolled in programs preparing them to enter the clinical field. This project aims to assess the relationship between types of insurance coverage and mental health service usage habits among students aiming to become mental health professionals. Sixty students attending California State University Fullerton (CSUF) intending to enter the mental health field were asked to participate in an anonymous, online, two-part survey. In the first half of this survey, students were asked to provide various forms of demographic information. Participants were then asked in the second half to answer questions regarding their mental health service usage habits since attending CSUF. The majority of these students reported being enrolled as human service majors, with obtained student gender reports consisting of female, male, and nonbinary. The findings of this research study will be useful in improving mental health services offered to college students due to its focus on the impact outside factors like health insurance may have on student utilization. Once students are brought into treatment, they appear to be more likely to view it as beneficial and thus to continue with care. Results suggest that while income and insurance status do not have an impact on student mental health usage habits, students who expressed a need for mental health treatment were less likely to seek out this care. Results also suggest that Counseling and Psychological Services (CAPS) is sufficiently capable of providing people with viable mental health support, as those who received treatment from CAPS were more likely to continue treatment elsewhere once their time with CAPS reached its end.

Insurance and Income Status and Mental Health Utilization among College Students

Introduction

In recent years, colleges across the country have seen the heavy toll mental health pays on the minds of their students, and the California State University (CSU) system is by no means an exception. As recently as last year, the Board of Behavioral Sciences (BBS) has made legislative efforts to improve the capacity for on-campus mental health care for currently enrolled students. Currently, the BBS requires campuses within the CSU system to hire, at minimum, one full-time mental health counselor per 1,500 students enrolled at each of its campuses. These counselors must be licensed in the state of California itself, holding them to the same standards as the counselors a student may encounter outside of the context of college enrollment (S.B. 11, 2023). Through the introduction of legislation passed through Congress fourteen years ago, students in the modern education system are now much more easily able to utilize the medical insurance benefits of their parents and legal guardians to access these counseling services. A subsequent extension of this national law changed the age at which dependents were removed from their household's insurance from 19 to 26, meaning that college students went from being uninsured to retaining the same access to care their parents received (Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act, 2010).

Even with these improvements in access, students appear hesitant to utilize mental health services. Among the most likely young adults to be covered under their parents' insurance are college students, especially compared to young adults with an education level below high school, stopping at high school, and even holding an advanced degree (Han et al., 2016). These insured young adults are also more likely to report having better access to care and better care utilization patterns (Han, 2016). However, young adults covered through private insurance providers

through their parents — either through direct payments or employment — are shown to use their insurance to seek out mental health treatment less than those who are covered through public insurance programs, though still more so than those insured through themselves or their spouse and those who are uninsured (Han et al., 2016). Bearing this difference in utilization in mind, the purpose of this project was to assess the role in which the type of medical insurance a college student in California is covered by plays in their utilization habits for mental health services.

Materials and Methods

Students attending California State University Fullerton (CSUF) intending to enter the mental health field ($n = 60$) were asked to participate in an anonymous, online, two-part survey hosted through the program Qualtrics. This survey was administered to students through links. In the first half of this survey, students were asked to provide various forms of demographic information. These responses consisted of information regarding student age, race and ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender identity, college major, college year or level, average units per semester, hours currently worked per week at a paid job, hours currently worked per week at an unpaid internship, household income, United States citizenship status, housing status, and medical insurance status. Participants were then asked in the second half to answer questions regarding their mental health service usage habits since attending CSUF. These responses consisted of information regarding student usage of treatment services offered through Counseling and Psychological Services (CAPS) and usage of treatment services offered through outside sources. Participants were asked not only if they utilized outside services but also why they chose not to use them based on their responses to previous questions. Participants who reported not continuing to receive treatment from outside sources after their time at CAPS came

to an end were asked why this was the case, with the same question being asked to those who expressed a conscious need for mental health services and did not receive them at all.

Results

Significant correlations of factors of interest ($p < .05$) were found between students receiving outside services versus receiving services from CAPS ($r = .296, p = .021$), receiving outside services versus continuing treatment after CAPS appointments were completed ($r = .725, p < .001$), and students recognizing a need for services versus receiving outside services ($r = -.261, p = 0.46$).

Additional correlations outside of factors of interest were found between student-reported income level versus insurance status ($r = -.257, p = .047$), age versus major ($r = -.288, p = .031$), age versus recognizing a need for services ($r = -.288, p = .027$), race/ethnicity versus major ($r = .278, p = .038$), and gender identity versus income level ($r = .353, p = .006$).

For populations and factors of interest, percentages have been compiled in data tables in subsequent pages. Tables have been provided to present student demographics based on insurance status (*Table 1*) and mental health service utilization (*Table 2*), as well as the relationships between insurance status and mental health service utilization (*Table 3*).

Discussion

The initial hypothesis of this project — whether insurance status impacts the types of services college students may be more willing to engage in — resulted in a lack of significant evidence to support it. Students were expected to prefer outside services if they were covered through private providers, an HMO program, or a PPO program, whereas students covered through public or needs criteria-based services such as Medical or indemnity insurance were

expected to prefer on-campus services. Alas, the correlations between these factors were insignificant, suggesting that the type of insurance a student is covered under for mental health treatment does not impact their choices regarding the services they utilize.

What results do provide us with, however, are two major points of interest that were not originally considered. CAPS appears to be a valuable source of mental health care and to be able to help students transfer towards further treatment effectively. Despite this, students also appear to be rather hesitant to actually receive mental health treatment of any kind, regardless of its source.

CAPS and Student Utilization

When assessing student experiences with Counseling and Psychological Services (CAPS), results suggest that CAPS serves as a valuable resource that aids students in processing forward in their mental health journey. Of the students who reported receiving treatment through CAPS ($n = 19$), 36.8% — over a third — also reported receiving services after they had reached the end of their sessions with CAPS (*Table 3*). Among students who received treatment from CAPS and then did not continue outside of it, their major concern appears to be a lack of time ($n = 25$). Considering the lives of college students, this is not a surprising result. Students most often reported being enrolled in 12 or more credits per semester ($n = 56$), working 0–6 hours per week at a paid job ($n = 18$), and 7–14 hours per week at an unpaid internship ($n = 29$).

At face value, this does not seem like much, but when you also consider the time students spend working on coursework outside of class, the responsibilities they may have at home, and the energy they put into their social lives with friends and loved ones, the sheer density of the daily lives can become exhausting. The fact that students who had completed their time at CAPS

are only concerned with time restraints suggests that not only is CAPS effectively able to aid students in distress, but it can also provide them with resources that diminish their concerns about costs for further treatment. This helps to create an avenue towards care should they be willing to take it. Counselors are likely able to guide students throughout the process of identifying the aspects of the care they need that can be afforded by them, especially based on factors such as their health insurance and current household income.

College Student Resistance to Care

However, the results yield a concerning reality about students attending CSUF. The percentage of students who reported a recognition of needing mental health services was 64.4% ($n = 38$), meaning that more than a third of the students who participated in this study who are in need of care avoid it (*Table 3*). Of these students, 26.3% ($n = 10$) — less than a third — of study participants who reported needing mental health services went to actually receive services, suggesting a high level of hesitancy among students to receive care. Additionally, when asked why they did not receive any form of treatment, the major reasons students reported were a lack of time ($n = 14$) and high costs ($n = 12$).

The potential implications of this are concerning, especially when taking into consideration the fact that all of the students involved in this study intend to enter the field of mental health itself. In California alone, mental health among college students is a massive concern. Previous research highlights this concern, with current evidence demonstrating just how adverse to treatment some students actually are. Roughly 19.0% of college students across 39 Californian college campuses reported experiencing serious psychological distress in the past 30 days, with 11.0% of students reporting significant academic impairment influenced by poor mental health within the past year (Sontag-Padilla et al., 2016). Only 20.0% of students reported

using mental health services, with an even split of 10.0% utilizing on-campus services and 10.0% utilizing off-campus services (Sontag-Padilla et al., 2016). Of the students surveyed within the CSU system ($n = 6,925$), 23.0% reported having used mental health services of any kind, with 12.0% utilizing on-campus services and 11.0% utilizing off-campus services (Sontag-Padilla et al., 2016).

Thankfully, our population appears to be slightly more willing to engage in mental health treatment, but this is no doubt due to having a sample size far smaller than that of this study. It is unclear if this increase is related to our population specifically showing interest in entering the mental health field themselves as professionals. Nevertheless, this contrast between data sets suggests that this resistance to care is not an isolated incident and, in fact, the result of an ongoing pattern among college students.

Student Crisis Intervention

Why is it, then, that students appear so reluctant to seek out treatment? Even when students are aware of the resources available to them and their need for mental health counseling and care, there is a heavy desire to avoid treatment. This resistance does not end once a student leaves college, either. In 2021, roughly 21.6% of adults in America reported having received mental health treatment (Terlizzi & Schiller, 2022). By contrast, an estimated 19.0% of American adults were identified as experiencing a mental illness in the same year, with 18.54% of the adult population in California alone experiencing crisis. To provide some perspective, this translates to roughly 47 million Americans and 5,566,000 California residents who are experiencing a mental health issue that had risen toward clinical concern (Reinert et al., 2020).

One likely explanation for this heavy trend of resistance may be found within the cycle of crisis and crisis intervention. The onset of a crisis can be a process that can easily overwhelm

individuals, and those who are unable to cope with the stress it brings properly may find themselves struggling to move forward in any aspect of their lives. Crisis itself can be divided into four steps, flowing from the event that perpetuates the crisis, the person's perception of danger or threat, the emotional distress born from this perception, and the subsequent application of coping mechanisms to address said distress (Kanel, 2018). In theory, should an individual be adequately equipped to handle their distress, they will be better able to move forward. However, in many cases, individuals do not try to receive support until they are in the depths of this crisis state, which leads to a rapid decrease in functioning levels and capabilities. Students are by no means immune to this cycle. When anyone, including a college student, begins to experience a crisis, they may provide pushback to themselves, using defensive tactics in an effort to ignore the emotional distress caused by the original event. This is especially true when a person seeks out counseling in the depths of a crisis state, where they are likely to confront wait lists or limitations in access that further encourage them to fight against themselves and their need for mental health care (Kanel, 2018). The end result of an event such as this only creates further capacity for crisis later down the line. Crisis is much like rot in that it will further weaken a person until it is resolved or otherwise addressed and maintained. Should the rot that has spread along the side of a wooden house be ignored, despite being recognized by the homeowner, it will continue to spread and weaken the building. The only solution is to address the rot and learn how to respond to it should it return in the future. Mental health concerns that are left unaddressed will not only continue to affect an individual, but they are likely to become more frequent. A crisis state may go from occurring once every few months to once every few days if not addressed properly, further creating declines in functioning levels that can lead to incredibly distressing outcomes, such as suicide, homicide, and even psychosis, depending on the case at hand (Kanel, 2018).

Suggestions for Further Research

The best course of action may not be the most readily available, especially in the common case of students avoiding care until crisis strikes. In an effort to combat this, CAPS has provided a digital program known as YOU@Fullerton, often shortened to simply YOU, providing a method of coping with the stress of college and their personal lives without the time constraints of seeking counsel the moment they are falling apart at the seams (*You@Fullerton*, 2022). In this project, students were not asked specifically about YOU and their experiences with it. Should this research be repeated or expanded upon, it is highly recommended to include questions regarding YOU. Additionally, it must be noted that this survey was provided to a limited sample size, consisting mostly of human service majors. While major had a significant relationship to care usage statistically, this is likely a false positive result. To truly understand if major plays a role in student mental health service utilization, this study would need to be repeated at a level open to all majors across the entire campus or focused within specific academic departments of interest. Lastly, questions regarding race/ethnicity, gender identity, and sexual orientation should always be assessed to ensure that students can accurately identify themselves, as well as to understand better the diversity of those who call this campus home.

Conclusion

Mental health treatment is far more complex than the access one has to it. Services can be offered in mass quantities, but they are useless if an individual does not feel a strong enough drive to engage with them while also being able to receive them in a timely manner. CAPS has demonstrated its usefulness to the students at California State University Fullerton, and it is likely to only improve over time. As mental health awareness and treatment continue to become normalized in the world of healthcare and daily life, it is critical to encourage students to utilize

the services provided to them. Even if all a student is doing is exploring the options available to them, it allows for the normalization of reaching out not only during, but prior to crisis. No one should have to struggle to exist within their own mind, and services for students like CAPS that provide them with a controlled space they can be safely and successfully transitioned out of is a worthwhile investment for all parties involved.

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Table 1. Study population demographics and reported insurance coverage status.

Demographic Variable		HMO/PPO	Medi-Cal	Private	Uninsured	Total
Age	18 - 21 (n=18, 30.0%)	7 (11.7%)	9 (15.0%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	18 (30.0%)
	22 - 26 (n=24, 40.0%)	13 (21.7%)	8 (13.3%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.0%)	24 (40.0%)
	27 - 40 (n=14, 23.3%)	7 (11.7%)	6 (10.0%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	14 (23.3%)
	41 - 64 (n=4, 6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	4 (6.7%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		27 (45.0%)	26 (43.3%)	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.3%)	60 (100.0%)
Race/Ethnicity	African American or Black (n=5, 8.3%)	3 (5.0%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.3%)
	Asian (n=5, 8.3%)	3 (5.0%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.3%)
	European American or White (n=10, 16.7%)	4 (6.7%)	4 (6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	10 (16.7%)
	Hispanic and/or Latino (n=33, 55.0%)	13 (21.7%)	16 (26.7%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.7%)	33 (55.0%)
	Multiracial/multicultural (n=4, 6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	3 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.7%)
	Other (n=3, 5.0%)	3 (5.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.0%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		27 (45.0%)	26 (43.3%)	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.3%)	60 (100.0%)
Sexuality	Straight (n=49, 81.7%)	20 (33.3%)	23 (38.3%)	2 (3.3%)	4 (6.7%)	49 (81.7)
	Lesbian (n=2, 3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)
	Bisexual (n=7, 11.7%)	5 (8.3%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	7 (11.7%)
	Pansexual (n=2, 3.3%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		27 (45.0%)	26 (43.3%)	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.3%)	60 (100.0%)
Gender	Male (n=12, 20.0%)	4 (6.7%)	6 (10.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)	12 (20.0%)
	Female (n=47, 78.3%)	22 (36.7%)	20 (33.3%)	2 (3.3%)	3 (5.0%)	47 (78.3%)
	Nonbinary (n=1, 1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		27 (45.0%)	26 (43.3%)	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.3%)	60 (100.0%)
Major	Human Services (n=50, 83.3%)	22 (39.3%)	22 (39.3%)	2 (3.6%)	4 (7.1%)	50 (89.3%)
	Psychology (n=4, 6.7%)	2 (3.6%)	2 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (7.1%)
	Sociology (n=2, 3.3%)	2 (3.6%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.6%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		26 (46.4%)	24 (42.9%)	2 (3.6%)	4 (7.1%)	56 (100.0%)

Table 2. Study population demographics and reported mental health utilization habits.

Demographic Variable	CAPS		Post Caps		Went outside CAPS		Thought but didn't go		
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Age	18 - 21 (n=18, 30.0%)	12 (20.0%)	6 (10.0%)	3 (15.8%)	3 (15.8%)	11 (18.3%)	7 (11.7%)	4 (6.8%)	13 (22.0%)
	22 - 26 (n=24, 40.0%)	16 (26.7%)	8 (13.3%)	5 (26.3%)	2 (10.5%)	16 (26.7%)	8 (13.3%)	7 (11.9%)	17 (28.8%)
	27 - 40 (n=14, 23.3%)	8 (13.3%)	6 (10.0%)	4 (21.1%)	2 (10.5%)	10 (16.7%)	4 (6.7%)	7 (11.9%)	7 (11.9%)
	41 - 64 (n=4, 6.7%)	4 (6.7%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)	2 (3.3%)	3 (5.1%)	1 (1.7%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	38 (64.4%)
		60 (100.0%)		19 (100.0%)		60 (100.0%)		59 (100.0%)	
Race/Ethnicity	African American or Black (n=5, 8.3%)	5 (8.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	3 (5.1%)
	Asian (n=5, 8.3%)	4 (6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.5%)
	European American or White (n=10, 16.7%)	6 (10.0%)	4 (6.7%)	2 (10.5%)	1 (5.3%)	4 (6.7%)	6 (10.0%)	6 (10.2%)	4 (6.8%)
	Hispanic and/or Latino (n=33, 55.0%)	22 (36.7%)	11 (18.3%)	6 (31.6%)	5 (26.3%)	22 (36.7%)	11 (18.3%)	13 (22.0%)	20 (33.9%)
	Multiracial/multicultural (n=4, 6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	3 (5.0%)	3 (15.8%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.3%)	2 (3.3%)	1 (1.7%)	3 (5.1%)
	Other (n=3, 5.0%)	2 (3.3%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (5.3%)	2 (3.3%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (5.1%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	38 (64.4%)
		60 (100.0%)		19 (100.0%)		60 (100.0%)		59 (100.0%)	
Sexuality	Straight (n=49, 81.7%)	34 (56.7%)	15 (25.0%)	10 (52.6%)	4 (21.2%)	33 (55.0%)	16 (26.7%)	20 (33.9%)	29 (49.2%)
	Lesbian (n=2, 3.3%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.4%)
	Bisexual (n=7, 11.7%)	3 (5.0%)	4 (6.7%)	1 (5.3%)	3 (15.8%)	3 (5.1%)	4 (6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	5 (8.5%)
	Pansexual (n=2, 3.3%)	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (5.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.4%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	38 (64.4%)
		60 (100.0%)		19 (100.0%)		60 (100.0%)		59 (100.0%)	
Gender	Male (n=12, 20.0%)	7 (11.7%)	5 (8.3%)	1 (5.3%)	3 (42.9%)	4 (6.67%)	8 (13.3%)	7 (11.9%)	5 (8.5%)
	Female (n=47, 78.3%)	33 (55.5%)	14 (23.3%)	10 (52.6%)	4 (21.1%)	35 (58.3%)	12 (20.0%)	14 (23.7%)	32 (54.2%)
	Nonbinary (n=1, 1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	38 (64.4%)
		60 (100.0%)		19 (100.0%)		60 (100.0%)		59 (100.0%)	
Major	Human Services (n=50, 83.3%)	34 (60.7%)	16 (28.6%)	9 (50.0%)	6 (33.3%)	31 (55.4%)	19 (33.9%)	20 (36.4%)	29 (52.7%)
	Psychology (n=4, 6.7%)	3 (5.4%)	1 (1.8%)	1 (5.6%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.8%)	3 (5.5%)
	Sociology (n=2, 3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.6%)	1 (5.6%)	1 (5.6%)	1 (1.8%)	1 (1.8%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.6%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)		37 (66.7%)	19 (33.3%)	11 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	36 (65.0%)	20 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	34 (64.4%)
		56 (100.0%)		18 (100.0%)		56 (100.0%)		55 (100.0%)	

Table 3. Reported insurance status and reported mental health utilization habits.

Insurance Status	CAPS		Post Caps		Went outside CAPS		Thought but didn't go	
	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Insurance Status HMO/PPO	18 (30.0%)	9 (15.0%)	4 (21.2%)	5 (26.3%)	17 (28.3%)	10 (16.7%)	12 (20.3%)	14 (23.7%)
Medi-Cal	16 (26.7%)	10 (16.7%)	7 (36.8%)	2 (10.5%)	16 (26.7%)	10 (16.7%)	8 (13.6%)	18 (30.5%)
Private	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (1.7%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.4%)
Uninsured	4 (6.7%)	1 (1.7%)	1 (5.3%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.7%)	4 (6.8%)
Total (n=60, 100.0%)	40 (66.7%)	20 (33.3%)	12 (63.2%)	7 (36.8%)	39 (65.0%)	21 (35.0%)	21 (35.6%)	38 (64.4%)
	60 (100.0%)		19 (100.0%)		60 (100.0%)		59 (100.0%)	
Correlations	r(58)=-.114	p=.384	r(17)=-.309	p=.119	r(58)=-.161	p=.219	r(57)=.195	p=.138